

DUNYODA INFLYATSIYANING AHOLI FAROVONLIGIGA, MAHSULOT VA XIZMATLAR TANNARXIGA SALBIY TA'SIRI

THE NEGATIVE IMPACT OF INFLATION IN THE WORLD ON THE WELL-BEING OF THE POPULATION, THE COST OF PRODUCTS AND SERVICES

НЕГАТИВНОЕ ВЛИЯНИЕ ИНФЛЯЦИИ В МИРЕ НА БЛАГОСОСТОЯНИЕ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ, СТОИМОСТЬ ТОВАРОВ И УСЛУГ

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ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada kundalik mahsulot va xizmatlarimiz iste'moliga salbiy va ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadigan inflyatsiya darajasi bizning turmush sharoitimizga ta'sirining mohiyati ta'kidlangan. Bundan tashqari, ushbu maqola ushbu muammoning echimini ko'rsatadi.

ANNOTATION

The article emphasizes the essence of the rate of inflation influences on our living condition which contains negative and positive effects on consumption of our daily products and services. Also, this article indicates the giving solution to this problem.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье подчеркивается суть влияния уровня инфляции на условия нашей жизни, которое содержит негативные и позитивные последствия для потребления наших повседневных товаров и услуг. Также в этой статье указано решение этой проблемы.

KALIT SO'ZLAR

inflyatsiya, pul, iste'mol narxi, bozor mexanizmlari, Markaziy Bank, naqd pulni tejash

KEYWORDS

inflation, money, consumer price, market mechanisms, Central Bank, cash saver

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

инфляция, деньги, потребительские цены, рыночные механизмы, Центральный банк, экономия наличных

INTRODUCTION

Inflation is the most important words in an economy, influences of this may distract from way of economy. In this article, we look through inflation, its rate and their effect on price of products and services with illustrating solutions.

In economics, inflation refers to a general progressive increase in prices of goods and services in the economy. When the general price level rises, each unit of currency buys fewer goods and services; consequently, inflation corresponds to a reduction in the purchasing power of money. The common measure of inflation is the inflation rate, the annualized percentage change in a general index. When it comes to the cost of living, a rising inflation measure means it has become more expensive to maintain our previous lifestyle. If your income hasn't increased over the measured period by at least the rate of inflation, then you're buying power will have fallen, as the costs of goods and services will have increased over that time. Inflation doesn't just affect our everyday expenses, but could also impact our savings, investments and pensions. The consequences of inflation: Inflation can have both positive and negative effects on social and economic processes.

MAIN PART

The positive effects of inflation include the following points:

Inflation has a stimulating effect on trade turnover as the expectation of higher prices in the future encourages consumers to buy goods today. Inflation serves as a factor in the "natural selection" of economic evolution. Under the conditions of inflationary economic development, weak enterprises go bankrupt. Thus, only the strongest and most efficient enterprises remain in the national economy. At the same time, inflation can contribute to the growth of the competitiveness of domestic goods. In addition to this, In an economy with underemployment, moderate inflation, while slightly reducing the real income of the population, makes them work harder and better. Inflation redistributes income between lenders and borrowers, with borrowers

benefiting too. Having received a long-term loan at a fixed interest rate, the borrower will have to pay back only part of it, as the real purchasing power of money will decrease due to inflation. Debtors, buyers, importers, and real-sector workers benefit from inflation.

The negative effects of inflation include the following points:

1. All monetary reserves (deposits, loans, account balances, etc.) depreciate. Thus, from unanticipated inflation, holders of savings in a current account lose income (money depreciates and savings decrease).

2. The problems of money issues are sharply exacerbated.

3. There is a spontaneous, uncontrolled redistribution of income in which creditors, sellers, exporters, and employees of state-owned enterprises lose out on inflation. Thus, creditors (those who issued the loan) expect to repay the loan with money that has lost its purchasing power.

4. The economic well-being of those who keep money savings in banks decreases if the usual bank interest rate is lower than the inflation rate.

5. Rising prices are accompanied by a fall in the exchange rate of the national monetary unit.

6. All major economic indicators, such as GDP, profitability, interest, etc., are distorted.

7. Inflation affects the volume of national production. For example, hyperinflation halts production and reduces sales of goods, products, work, and services, which in turn leads to a decrease in real national production, an increase in unemployment, enterprise closures, and bankruptcy.

For example:

Cash savers could be hit particularly badly, as the purchasing power of our money falls. Consider the following example: if you invest the amount needed to buy a car into a bank account for 5-years – at an annual interest rate of 1% – and the cost of cars over the same period

increases by 2% per annum, then at the end of the period you would need to add more money to be able to buy the car. Think about how the cost of living has already changed since you were a child. A high rate of inflation combined with a low rate of interest, means the money we have saved in potentially poorly performing savings accounts could be seriously hit, having a detrimental effect for cash savers. If inflation, as is usually the case, is higher than interest rates, then in real terms your returns will become negative, meaning you may want to think about whether cash is the best place to stay in the long-term (for instance, high street savings accounts and cash ISAs.) You could consider alternative methods for saving, such as investing in assets that have traditionally increased at a higher rate than inflation. Options could include considering investments that are inflation-linked, like some National Savings Accounts or government loans, investing in property, or in stocks and shares.

Retirees. For those saving for their retirement, high rates of inflation can erode the buying power of your pension fund when you need it. If you have a defined benefit pension scheme that escalates in payment by CPI, this is a huge advantage. However, those retirees reliant on fixed annuity pension income will see the future buying power of their fixed pension diminish, as bills and prices rise. If you're saving for retirement, it's vital that investment performance of funds (after all costs) is monitored regularly. Where a fund's performance – measured over a reasonable period – fail to beat the rate of inflation, then alternative strategies should be considered to ensure that funds are growing in real terms. It's important to understand that the cost of an income that rises with inflation and is therefore protected, is significantly more costly than a level income.

The most well-known indicator of inflation is the Consumer Price Index (CPI), which measures the percentage change in the price of a basket of goods and services consumed by households.

To better understand how inflation is calculated we can use an example. In this example we calculate inflation for a basket that has two items in it – books and childcare. The formula for calculating inflation for a single item is below. To better understand how inflation is calculated we can use an example. In this example we calculate inflation for a basket

$$\text{Inflation} = \left(\frac{\text{price}(\text{year}2) - \text{price}(\text{year}1)}{\text{price}(\text{year}1)} \right) * 100\%$$

Price (year 2)- the last price of products or services
 Price (year 1)- It means previous price of products and services

For instance, the car costs 20000\$ currently. However, consumers could buy that kind of car 150000\$ last year. The inflation rate will be 33% according to this information above.

Consumer price index (CPI) for the Republic of Uzbekistan in September 2021 by January 2020 amounted to 117 % The overall CPI decline over the selected period was 17 %

First of all, we have started to truly implement market principles for the last 3 years, while other countries did it 30 years ago. Namely, price liberalization measures have been taken only in recent years," said the head of the Central Bank of Uzbekistan.

The head of the Central Bank called "the second objective reason" for the price rise the "investment hunger" that's been formed after 27 years. According to him, by order of the president investment activity in the regions is increasing,

but it requires an infusion of additional funds and resources in the economy. "This, in turn, is done through the allocation of the bank, investment loans, public resources. This, accordingly, leads to an increase in the amount of money in the economy, which affects inflation.

The third reason is the liberalization of the currency market. As the head of the regulator noted, in all countries, where the currency market was freed from government restrictions, inflation increased several times.

Solution. Fighting inflation is one of the most complex issues of economic policy. Ways to reduce inflation are ambiguous and contradictory in their consequences. The main methods of fighting inflation are monetary reforms and anti-inflationary policy. Monetary reform is a complete or partial transformation of the monetary system, carried out by the state to streamline and strengthen money circulation. The anti-inflationary policy is a set of measures of state regulation of the economy, aimed at suppressing inflation.

Measures to move against inflation

To solve the problem of inflation, it is necessary to develop a certain set of measures aimed at strengthening market mechanisms and the confidence of the majority of the population in the government, for which it is extremely important to reduce, and then extinguish inflationary expectations. To activate market mechanisms, it is first of all necessary to support small business and entrepreneurship, to facilitate the free flow of capital from industry to industry and to prevent the emergence of monopoly.

The fight against inflation is a set of measures aimed at comprehensive stimulation of the economy while limiting (limiting) the money supply. Limits should exist for exactly as long as necessary, regardless of the state of the budget and unemployment. The limit should help stabilize price growth and reduce demand pressures by stabilizing expectations. These measures lead to a change in the ratio between the saving and the consuming parts of income in favour of savings. It is very important to

constantly carry out actions to reduce the budget deficit by reducing the expenditure side. Sharp reductions in expenditures can provoke deepening social tensions, so it is necessary to identify in advance the possible socio-economic consequences and to implement the planned measures gradually. In the period of inflation, well-thought-out and well-organized privatization can help to reduce demand, which can draw the large mass of money from the demand market to itself, and on the other hand, sold enterprises go off the balance sheet of the state budget, easing the fate of the latter.

CONCLUSION

One of the measures of complex measures to combat inflation can be a massive consumer import, which at the same time can siphon off a large share of circulating money. The government can influence the reduction of the money supply by issuing government securities for sale. The main objective of all measures is to reduce inflation to the lowest possible rate, stabilize prices and the standard of living of the population and create conditions for the development of production.

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